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A machine learning based approach with an augmented dataset for fatigue life prediction of additively manufactured Ti-6Al-4V samples

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the prediction of fatigue life using a machine learning (ML) approach. The original dataset is based on the parameters of defects obtained by micro-computed tomography (μ -CT) prior to fatigue tests, stress level and the fatigue life of additively manufactured (AM) Ti-6Al-4V samples. As the original dataset is considered too small to train a comprehensive ML model, the study proposed a novel approach for dataset augmentation. Dataset augmentation is done using inverse transform sampling and multivariate radial basis function (RBF) interpolation with various values of the smoothing parameter (λ). Finally, ML model accuracy is improved up to 0.953 of coefficient of determination (R^2).

1. Introduction

Fatigue resistance is one of the most important and monitored properties of materials used in the automotive or aerospace industry. One of the major concerns is whether the additively manufactured (AM) samples can meet the expected fatigue life. Defects induced by the three-dimensional printing process always influence fatigue behavior [1]. For ductile metallic materials, the fatigue endurance of AM parts presents a higher sensitivity to defects [2,3,4]. Imperfections caused by the AM process are mainly porosity and lack of fusion (LOF) [2,5]. Even if the porosity portion can be optimized to as low as 0.2 %, the presence of defects is still a major factor for fatigue-critical applications [6,7,8]. Therefore, non-destructive testing (NDT) is a fundamental part of the process when assessing the quality of fabrication in AM parts [9]. The NDT method, called X-ray micro-computed tomography (μ -CT), is commonly used as an instrument to obtain detailed information about the defects, such as the size, shape and distribution of dense titanium AM parts [10,8]. The μ -CT technique uses X-rays to create cross-sections of a material microstructure that can be used to create a virtual three-dimensional model without destroying the original object [11].

The defects located deep below the surface and near the surface have different impacts on the fatigue behavior of the AM parts. The randomly distributed defects tend to cause higher scatter in terms of cycles to failure. However, parts with defects positioned close to the surface in smaller numbers can sustain higher stress amplitude [3,12]. Similarly, the fatigue behavior decreases with increasing critical near-surface defect size despite the difference in the number of inner defects [13,14,15]. In addition, a negative correlation

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Nomenclature

2SKST	Two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test
A_{defect}	Area of defect
A_{sphere}	Area of sphere with the volume as the defect
AB	As-built
ANN	Artificial neural networks
AM	Additive manufacturing (or additively manufactured)
APE	Absolute percentage error
BO	Bayesian optimization
c	Centre point of RBF
CNC	Computer numerical control
CV	Cross-validation
D	Observed dataset
\bar{D}	Average diameter of the defects per sample
\bar{D}_{norm}	Scaled average diameter of the defects per sample
D_{test}	Test set
$D_{train, aug}$	Augmented training set
$D_{train, exp}$	Experimental training set
DT	Decision tree
DT_D	Maximum depth of DT
DT_M	Number of DTs
DT_S	Minimal portion of samples to split
ECDF	Empirical cumulative distribution function
EI	Expected improvement of TPE
EP	Electropolished
f	Prediction model of GBR
GBR	Gradient boosting regressor
GMM	Gaussian mixture model
GS	Grid search
H_0	Null hypothesis for 2SKST
H_a	Alternative hypothesis for 2SKST
HPO	Hyperparameter optimization
I	Identity matrix in RBF
I_{RBF}	RBF interpolator
J	Indicator function of ECDF
k	Number of TPE trials
K	Matrix of RBF kernels
KS_c	Kolmogorov-Smirnov critical value
KS_D	Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic
l	Number of rounds during the CV
\bar{L}	Average location of the defects per sample
L_{GBR}	Loss function of GBR
\bar{L}_{norm}	Scaled average location of the defects per sample
$\log N$	Logarithmic fatigue life
LOOCV	Leave-one-out cross-validation
ML	Machine learning
n	Number of instances (or values)
n_{aug}	Number of augmented samples
n_d	Number of defects per sample
n_s	Number of samples
n_{test}	Number of test samples
n_{train}	Number of training samples
P	Matrix of RBF monomials
Q	Indicator function of GBR
r	Pseudo-residuals of GBR
R	Stress ratio
R^2	Coefficient of determination
RBF	Radial basis function

$RMSE$	Root mean squared error
\overline{RMSE}	Average of root mean squared error
ROI	Range of interest
RS	Random search
s	Radius of RBF
\bar{S}	Average sphericity of the defects per sample
\bar{S}_{norm}	Scaled average sphericity of the defects per sample
SLM	Selective laser melting (or melted)
TPE	Tree-structured Parzen estimator
X	Input matrix of independent variables
X_{aug}	Augmented set of X
X_{test}	Test set of X
X_{train}	Training set of experimental samples of X
y	Output vector of dependent variable
y_{aug}	Augmented set of y
y_{pred}	Predicted logarithmic life
y_{test}	Test set of y
y_{train}	Training set of y
\bar{y}_{true}	Average validation value of logarithmic life
α	Significance level
γ	Output parameter of GBR
η	Learning rate of GBR
H	Observation history of TPE
λ	Smoothing parameter of RBF
σ_a	Experimental stress amplitude
$\sigma_{a,norm}$	Scaled stress amplitude
φ	Kernel of RBF
ω	Hyperparameter configuration
ω^*	Optimal hyperparameter configuration
Ω	Hyperparameter search space

occurs between the fatigue life and the defect size of the AM under the same applied stress level [16].

To model the prediction of fatigue life, the empirical approach (Manson-Coffin equation [17]) or the analytical approach (Murakami [18]) provides the information needed to evaluate the fatigue life of AM parts with inner defects, allowing further quantification of the sensitivity of fatigue behavior to defects [19,20]. Methods based on the Murakami parameter ($\sqrt{\text{area}}$) directly correlate defect properties with the fatigue endurance by the generalized Kitagawa-Takahashi diagram [2,21]. However, overestimation of the critical defect can provide a conservative prediction of fatigue life [22,23]. Unfortunately, the deterministic methods are not well suited when the defects are randomly distributed in the AM parts and have highly complex shapes. Nevertheless, for stochastic problems, the machine learning (ML) models represent an effective and capable approach [24,25,26]. The ML regression models were used for fatigue life prediction of AM Ti-6Al-4V parts in several studies [27,28,29]. Furthermore, defect-based XGBoost and artificial neural networks (ANN) models for fatigue life prediction of AM metals were employed [30,31]. Nevertheless, generalized trained ML models with a high prediction accuracy for unseen data require large amounts of data, which is time consuming and very expensive. Therefore, it is meaningful to develop a novel procedure that will effectively address the problems with smaller datasets.

Li et al. [29] proposed a Monte Carlo simulation for dataset augmentation and ANN model to investigate the impact of defect size, depth, location and build orientation on AM Ti-6Al-4V samples manufactured by selective laser melting (SLM) technology. Nevertheless, the model considered the defects' parameters to be a univariate function of stress amplitude during data augmentation, which ignores the interaction between independent variables. Shi et al. [32] used several interpolation algorithms for augmented datasets, such as nearest neighbor interpolation and linear interpolation. Furthermore, the probability Gaussian mixture model (GMM) was used, which assumes that all data points are generated from the mixed distribution of limited Gaussian distributions. He et al. [33] applied generative adversarial networks to enlarge multi-axis fatigue datasets, thus increasing the prediction accuracy of the ML model. Shen et al. [34] introduced synthetic sample generation using a GMM-based algorithm, which has been proven to increase the prediction ability of the ML model.

This study proposes a novel approach to the dataset augmentation process. Because the main purpose of dataset augmentation is to increase the prediction ability of the ML model, the augmented data are mainly based on the distribution of the test set. The inverse transform sampling using multivariate empirical cumulative distribution function (ECDF) and multivariate radial basis function (RBF) interpolation with cubic polyharmonic spline kernel with various values of the smoothing (regularization) parameter is applied to enlarge the dataset size. The ECDF is the distribution step function related with the empirical measure of a sample [35]. The RBF interpolation is an advanced method in approximation theory for constructing high-order accurate interpolants of unstructured data, possibly in high-dimensional spaces [36]. The usage of the RBF has been proven to be effective and flexible in various engineering

applications [37,38]. Furthermore, the proposed algorithm uses the gradient boosting regressor (GBR) as a ML model. The GBR model belongs to the category of ensemble ML algorithms. The fatigue life of AM parts can be predicted using various ensemble ML algorithms, such as the random forest regressor model [27,39,32] or the extreme gradient boosting regressor (regularized form of GBR) model in the study of Hao et al. [40]. However, the usage of ML models presents challenge in terms of the setting of the optimal values of hyperparameters. Hence, these hyperparameters are tuned in the optimization loop using several approaches. The most widely used approach is grid search (GS) optimization. GS determines the optimal value by investigating all the values in the search space. Recently, it has been used to model the fatigue life prediction of AM samples [27,28,39]. Another approach is called random search (RS). The RS algorithm tries a fixed number of pseudo-random values of hyperparameters from a specified distribution. Based on the study by Bergstra and Bengio [41], RS is more effective than GS. Furthermore, the genetic algorithm was applied for the optimization of ANN model used for fatigue life prediction [42,43]. Another group of optimization processes is based on the Bayesian optimization (BO) algorithm. The BO adopts the Gaussian process to continuously update the information from the prior value considering the previous parameter. A variant of the BO algorithm is a tree-structured Parzen estimator (TPE). The TPE is used in this study to tune the hyperparameters of the GBR model. The TPE algorithm has been widely used to tune the ML models in various applications, such as image processing [44,45] electricity price prediction [46], and fatigue evaluation of notched alloys used in aerospace [40].

This paper deals with the prediction of fatigue life using a ML approach. The original dataset is based on the parameters of defects obtained by μ -CT prior to fatigue tests, stress level and the fatigue life of Ti-6Al-4V samples manufactured using the SLM method. As the original dataset is considered too small to train a comprehensive ML model, the study proposed a novel approach for dataset augmentation. Overall, the paper is structured as follows: experimental procedures and dataset normalization are presented in Section 2. Section 3 describes the algorithm of the GBR model. Section 4 presents the proposed algorithm for fatigue life prediction (dataset augmentation, multivariate RBF interpolation, tuning hyperparameters using the TPE algorithm). Section 5 presents the results of the fatigue life prediction and discussion. Finally, the conclusions are summarized in Section 6.

2. Dataset establishment

2.1. Experimental data

The AM Ti-6Al-4V samples used for the dataset are taken from the study by Horñas et al. [27]. The geometry of the sample, pre-processing and post-processing treatments, and final surface roughness are detailly described in the origin paper. Three batches were manufactured with the total amount of 29 samples (see Table 1). Namely, an as built (AB) batch of 10 samples without any surface finish, then a batch of 10 samples milled by computer numerical control (CNC), and lastly an electropolished (EP) batch of 9 samples.

Table 1

Type of batch, experimental and scaled variables for each sample. The batches and the values of σ_a and $\log N$ from fatigue tests are taken from study by Horñas et al. [27]. The parameters of defect (n_d , \bar{D} , \bar{L} and \bar{S}) are obtained from post-processing of μ -CT measurement using the module called EasyPore (see Section 2.1).

No.	Batch	n_d	\bar{D}	\bar{D}_{norm}	\bar{L}	\bar{L}_{norm}	\bar{S}	\bar{S}_{norm}	σ_a	$\sigma_{a,norm}$	$\log N$	Test/Training set
1	AB	711	38.02	0.03	203.65	0.12	0.91	0.96	300	0.14	5.46	Training
2	AB	434	43.59	0.26	193.66	0.10	0.90	0.84	600	1.00	3.86	Test
3	AB	402	41.32	0.17	167.92	0.06	0.88	0.69	500	0.71	4.31	Training
4	AB	737	40.02	0.11	193.14	0.10	0.90	0.87	500	0.71	4.18	Test
5	AB	573	38.17	0.03	192.52	0.10	0.90	0.91	250	0.00	5.35	Test
6	AB	636	37.78	0.02	182.98	0.08	0.91	0.94	600	1.00	3.95	Training
7	AB	579	38.05	0.03	196.95	0.11	0.89	0.83	500	0.71	4.30	Training
8	AB	887	40.82	0.15	195.73	0.11	0.89	0.82	400	0.43	4.59	Test
9	AB	1488	37.35	0.00	265.42	0.23	0.90	0.87	350	0.29	4.98	Test
10	AB	698	38.41	0.04	179.31	0.08	0.90	0.88	400	0.43	4.72	Training
11	CNC	314	54.29	0.71	570.22	0.79	0.84	0.34	400	0.43	4.37	Test
12	CNC	356	61.05	1.00	684.11	1.00	0.81	0.14	600	1.00	3.99	Training
13	CNC	293	54.87	0.74	544.87	0.75	0.79	0.00	250	0.00	5.03	Training
14	CNC	357	43.92	0.28	573.79	0.80	0.85	0.47	350	0.29	4.71	Test
15	CNC	351	52.00	0.62	588.35	0.83	0.81	0.14	600	1.00	3.76	Test
16	CNC	845	39.83	0.10	583.33	0.82	0.88	0.74	400	0.43	4.69	Training
17	CNC	551	41.98	0.20	475.49	0.62	0.89	0.76	300	0.14	5.05	Training
18	CNC	657	38.52	0.05	520.73	0.70	0.90	0.85	300	0.14	5.05	Training
19	CNC	276	48.43	0.47	620.42	0.88	0.83	0.28	250	0.00	5.25	Training
20	CNC	728	58.00	0.87	579.56	0.81	0.80	0.03	350	0.29	4.33	Training
21	EP	524	39.96	0.11	202.95	0.12	0.90	0.85	300	0.14	5.33	Training
22	EP	741	39.75	0.10	239.39	0.19	0.90	0.87	350	0.29	4.56	Training
23	EP	456	54.05	0.70	388.84	0.46	0.84	0.35	600	1.00	3.79	Training
24	EP	388	40.96	0.15	251.80	0.21	0.90	0.84	400	0.43	4.70	Training
25	EP	399	38.31	0.04	229.83	0.17	0.91	1.00	250	0.00	5.47	Training
26	EP	449	38.84	0.06	235.73	0.18	0.91	0.97	600	1.00	4.01	Training
27	EP	466	40.89	0.15	136.84	0.00	0.91	0.99	350	0.29	4.92	Training
28	EP	689	38.64	0.05	178.76	0.08	0.91	0.94	500	0.71	4.29	Test
29	EP	427	38.26	0.04	207.32	0.13	0.91	0.93	400	0.43	4.62	Training

The surface roughness was analyzed in the previous article [27] and significant surface effect was not proved.

The manufactured samples were scanned using μ -CT prior to the fatigue tests. The μ -CT measurements were carried out using a Nanotom 180NF (GE Phoenix, X-ray) micro-focus XCT system. The central part of each sample was scanned at a voxel size of $5 \mu\text{m}$ resulting in a region of interest (ROI) of 9 mm in height. The ROI, assigned coordinate system during the μ -CT measurement and examples of defects distributions (three-dimensional renderings) are shown in Fig. 1. Optimal scanning parameters were acquired during an optimization study by means of μ -CT simulation [47]. The acceleration voltage was accordingly set to 130 kV using a current of $130 \mu\text{A}$ and an exposure time of 800 ms . Per scan, 1500 projections were acquired. Post-processing including a median filter with a three-dimensional kernel was performed in VGSTUDIO MAX 3.5 (Volume Graphics GmbH). In VGSTUDIO MAX, the porosity of each sample was analyzed using the module named EasyPore. The relative contrast value of 60% was empirically defined and the minimal pore size (volume) was set to 27 voxel [48]. The number of defects (n_d) detected for each sample is listed in Table 1.

The main subject of the presented work is prediction of the fatigue life without retrospective analysis (e.g., fractography). Therefore, the arithmetic mean (average) is used as a quantification parameter of overall quality for each sample and defect parameter. The average is one of the most popular values to summarize data [49].

Three defect parameters were analyzed for each sample (see Fig. 1). Parameter \bar{D} describes the average of diameter of circumscribed sphere of the defects per sample. Another parameter \bar{L} indicates the average location (minimal perpendicular distance from the free surface of the sample) of the defects in plane XY per sample. Finally, the parameter \bar{S} represents the average sphericity of the defect.

Individual sphericity S per defect is expressed by Eq. (1):

$$S_{i,j} = \frac{A_{\text{sphere},i,j}}{A_{\text{defect},i,j}} \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, n_s \tag{1}$$

where A_{sphere} is the subvoxel accurate area of sphere with the same volume as the defect and A_{defect} is the subvoxel accurate area of the respective j -th defect of the i -th sample ($n_s = 29$).

Arithmetic means of the defects' parameters for each sample are expressed by the following formulas:

Fig. 1. The range of interest (ROI), examples of defects distribution measured by μ -CT method and definition of defect parameters.

$$\bar{D}_i = \frac{1}{n_{d,i}} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{d,i}} D_{i,j} \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, n_s \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{L}_i = \frac{1}{n_{d,i}} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{d,i}} L_{i,j} \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, n_s \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{S}_i = \frac{1}{n_{d,i}} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{d,i}} S_{i,j} \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, n_s \quad (4)$$

where i is the number of samples ($n_s = 29$), $n_{d,i}$ is the number of defects of i -th sample.

The fatigue tests were performed with a constant load amplitude and stress ratio $R = -1$ (tension-compression), more details are described in the origin article [27]. The logarithmic fatigue life ($\log N$) and stress amplitude (σ_a) values have been obtained from the completed fatigue tests.

The final dataset of all observed variables is then divided into the independent variables and the dependent variable. The observed values are shown using boxplot in Fig. 2 and listed in Table 1.

2.2. Normalization of the dataset

To build the ML model with high degree of generalization ability, it is necessary that the values are expressed in the same order of magnitude. Data normalization means scaling independent variables to a given interval. The negative influence of independent variables with large variance is reduced by scaling the dataset. Besides, data normalization accelerates the convergence of the GBR model [50]. In this research, the Min-Max Normalization is applied by mapping the data into a range $[0, 1]$. The transformation is captured in Eq. (5):

$$X_{i,norm} = \frac{X_i - X_{i,min}}{X_{i,max} - X_{i,min}} \text{ for } X_i \in \{\bar{D}, \bar{L}, \bar{S}, \sigma_a\} \quad (5)$$

where $X_{i,norm}$ denotes the normalized values of the i -th variable of the dataset, X_{min} and X_{max} are the minimum and maximum values of the raw data respectively, X_i represents the original values of the corresponding feature. Scaled values of the independent variables are listed in Table 1.

3. Gradient boosting regressor model

The gradient boosting regressor (GBR) model is a supervised ML ensemble algorithm. The basic principle of the model is to combine weak prediction models into a stronger one to improve the prediction accuracy [51]. The decision trees (DTs) are used for the prediction models. In this article, the GBR model is coded in Python 3.10.6 using the Scikit-learn 1.2.2 package [52]. The algorithm of the DT contains built-in feature selection method during training of model. Therefore, the analysis of feature selection is not needed before application of the GBR model.

In the original dataset $D = \{(X_i, y_i)\}_{i=1,2,\dots,n}$, n stands for the number of instances, X_i represents the input matrix of independent variables (\bar{D}_{norm} , \bar{L}_{norm} , \bar{S}_{norm} and $\sigma_{a,norm}$), y_i corresponds to the output vector of the dependent variable ($\log N$) of sample i . The training DTs are denoted as DT_m , where $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$.

Fig. 2. Observed experimental data for all samples of (A) independent variables: average diameter of defects per sample (\bar{D}), average location of defects per sample (\bar{L}), average sphericity of defects per sample (\bar{S}) and stress amplitude (σ_a); (B) dependent variable: logarithmic fatigue life ($\log N$).

The initial weak prediction model is expressed by the following equations:

$$f_0(X_i) = \operatorname{argmin}_{\gamma} \sum_{i=1}^n L_{GBR}(y_i, \gamma) \tag{6}$$

$$L_{GBR}(y_i, \gamma) = (y_i - \gamma)^2 \tag{7}$$

where γ is the output parameter of the initial leaf nodes to minimize the loss value, $L_{GBR}(y_i, \gamma)$ is the loss function and is described as a square error. After each iteration, the so-called pseudo-residuals are calculated as the negative gradient of the loss function:

$$r_{m,i} = - \left[\frac{\partial L_{GBR}(y_i, f(X_i))}{\partial f(X_i)} \right]_{f(X_i)=f_{m-1}(X_i)} \quad \text{for } m = 1, 2, \dots, M; \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \tag{8}$$

where $r_{m,i}$ represents the pseudo-residual of the m -th iteration of the i -th instance, M is the number of the DT_m , $f(X_i)$ denotes the estimated logarithmic fatigue life for the current iteration and $f_{m-1}(X_i)$ for the previous. The DT_m is assembled using the training set $\{(X_i, r_{m,i})\}_{i=1,2,\dots,n}$ and its feature space of the leaf nodes is represented as $R_{m,j}$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, J$, where j is the number of features in the feature space and J is the maximum value. The output parameters of the leaf nodes in the j -th feature unit of the DT_m can be evaluated by:

$$\gamma_{m,j} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\gamma} \sum_{X_i \in R_{m,j}} L_{GBR}(y_i, f_{m-1}(X_i) + \gamma) \tag{9}$$

The fatigue life calculated in the m -th iteration can be expressed as follows:

$$f_m(X_i) = f_{m-1}(X_i) + \eta \sum_{j=1}^J \gamma_{m,j} Q \tag{10}$$

$$Q = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } X_i \in R_{m,j} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \tag{11}$$

where Q is the indicator function, η is the learning rate (shrinkage parameter) of the model. After the M -th iteration, the final GBR model can be written as follows:

Fig. 3. Schema of the GBR model.

Fig. 4. Flowchart of the proposed algorithm: (A) split of the scaled dataset; (B) dataset augmentation; (C) tuning of the hyperparameters of the GBR model by the TPE algorithm with 20-fold CV; (D) evaluation of the prediction accuracy.

$$f_M(X_i) = f_0(X_i) + \sum_{m=1}^M \eta \sum_{j=1}^J \gamma_{m,j} Q \tag{12}$$

The schema of the GBR model is shown in Fig. 3.

4. The proposed algorithm for fatigue life prediction

The proposed framework is divided into four stages, which are shown in Fig. 4A–D. Each stage is described in more detail in the following subchapters.

4.1. Split of the dataset

A normalized dataset must be split into a training and a test set in order to prevent biasing the accuracy of the GBR model. The test (~31 % of the total amount, $n_{test} = 9$) and training samples (~69 % of the total amount, $n_{train} = 20$) were pseudo-randomly selected using Python’s library named NumPy 1.24.3 and function called RandomState [53]. The function is based on the Mersenne-Twister pseudo-random number generator (MT19937) [54]. The generated training and test samples are listed in Table 1.

4.2. Dataset augmentation

In general, sparse datasets can lead to the overfitting of the ML model, which means that a model is trained too well and unable to predict unseen data precisely beyond the training set. A higher level of variance and a small dataset size contribute to the overfitting very easily. Hence, the level of generalization of the ML model is very weak. As the original dataset is considered too small to train a comprehensive ML model, a solution to this problem is needed. Therefore, the dataset augmentation is applied using inverse transform sampling and multivariate interpolation by RBF with various values (20 in total) of the smoothing parameter

Fig. 5. (A) Box plots of X_{test} , X_{train} and X_{aug} for each independent variable (\bar{D}_{norm} , \bar{L}_{norm} , \bar{S}_{norm} and $\sigma_{a,norm}$); (B) ECDF curves of X_{test} and X_{aug} for \bar{D}_{norm} , \bar{L}_{norm} , \bar{S}_{norm} and $\sigma_{a,norm}$ with computed value for two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (KS_D).

$\lambda \in \{1.0 \times 10^{-4}, 2.5 \times 10^{-4}, \dots, 2.5, 7.5\}$. The augmentation process is depicted in Fig. 4B and will be explained in more detail in the following subchapters.

4.2.1. Inverse transform sampling

The augmented input matrix of the independent variables denoted as X_{aug} is derived from the joint empirical cumulative distribution function (ECDF) of the original independent variables in the test set X_{test} . The ECDF can be expressed by the following equation [55]:

$$E_{X_{test}} = \frac{1}{n_{test}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{test}} J(\bar{D}_{norm,i}, \bar{L}_{norm,i}, \bar{S}_{norm,i}, \sigma_{a,norm,i}) \tag{13}$$

$$J = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } \bar{D}_{norm,i} \cap \bar{L}_{norm,i} \cap \bar{S}_{norm,i} \cap \sigma_{a,norm,i} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \tag{14}$$

where n_{test} is the number of samples in a test set and J is the indicator function. The estimator $E_{X_{test}}$ is a step function, showing jumps of size $\frac{1}{n_{test}}$ in each observation $\bar{D}_{norm,i} \cap \bar{L}_{norm,i} \cap \bar{S}_{norm,i} \cap \sigma_{a,norm,i}$ and staying constant between two consecutive observations. In this study, the total amount of augmented samples is $n_{aug} = 1000$. Afterwards, the values of the augmented input matrix X_{aug} are calculated from the inverse transform function of ECDF of original data as follows:

$$X_{aug} = E_{X_{test}}^{-1}(T, U, V, W) \text{ for } T, U, V, W \in [0, 1] \tag{15}$$

where T, U, V, W are uniformly generated 1000 values and $E_{X_{test}}^{-1}$ is the generalized inverse transform function. Furthermore, univariate ECDF curves for each independent variable are shown in Fig. 5B. Looking at the ECDF curves, the distribution trends of various variables are relatively close. In summary, if the ECDF curves of various variables in augmented data and original data are similar, then the characteristics of original data are well represented, and the ML algorithms should have decent prediction performance. The comparison between original and augmented data is done using the two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (2SKST) in the following subchapter. In addition, all input matrixes (X_{test} , X_{train} and X_{aug}) are shown by box plots in Fig. 5A.

4.2.2. Two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

Suppose that we want to test the null hypothesis between the ECDF of the experimental test set $E_{X_{test},i}$ where i denotes the i -th independent variable, $i \in \{\bar{D}_{norm}, \bar{L}_{norm}, \bar{S}_{norm}, \sigma_{a,norm}\}$, and the augmented set $E_{X_{aug},i}$:

$$H_0 : E_{X_{test},i}(\bullet) = E_{X_{aug},i}(\bullet) \tag{16}$$

versus the general alternative hypothesis:

$$H_a : E_{X_{test},i}(\bullet) \neq E_{X_{aug},i}(\bullet) \tag{17}$$

making a non-parametric assumption about the shape of the ECDF. This is known as the homogeneity test between two samples [56]. The test of whether two underlying univariate ECDF differ can be performed using the two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic (KS_D). The 2SKST can also be executed under general conditions that allow for heterogeneity, discontinuity, and dependence between samples [57].

KS_D is defined as:

$$KS_{D_{n_{test},n_{aug},i}} = \sup_x |E_{X_{test},n_{test},i}(x) - E_{X_{aug},n_{aug},i}(x)| \tag{18}$$

where $\sup(\bullet)$ is a supremum function, n_{test} is the number of samples in a test set ($n_{test} = 9$), n_{aug} is the number of samples in the augmented set ($n_{aug} = 1000$).

The H_0 is rejected at significance level α if [58]:

$$KS_{D_{n_{test},n_{aug},i}} > KS_{c_{n_{test},n_{aug}}} \tag{19}$$

Table 2
Two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for $\alpha = 0.05$.

Variable	KS_D	n_{test}	n_{aug}	KS_c	$KS_{D,i} > KS_c?$
\bar{D}_{norm}	0.112	9	1000	0.455	H_0 is not rejected
\bar{L}_{norm}	0.223	9	1000	0.455	H_0 is not rejected
\bar{S}_{norm}	0.112	9	1000	0.455	H_0 is not rejected
$\sigma_{a,norm}$	0.223	9	1000	0.455	H_0 is not rejected

$$KS_{c_{n_{test}, n_{aug}}} = \sqrt{-\ln\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right) \frac{1 + \frac{n_{aug}}{n_{test}}}{2n_{aug}}} \tag{20}$$

where $KS_{c_{n_{test}, n_{aug}}}$ is called a Kolmogorov-Smirnov critical value. The analysis of H_0 at $\alpha = 0.05$ for each variable is captured in Table 2. The H_0 is not rejected for any variable, so is assumed that X_{test} is well represented by X_{aug} .

4.2.3. Multivariate interpolation

For the four-dimensional interpolation problem the radial basis function (RBF) is applied using Python’s library SciPy 1.10.1 with function called RBFInterpolator [59]. The number of dimensions is equal to the number of the independent variables. The radius of the RBF is a scalar-valued function whose values at x can be expressed in terms of the following equation:

$$s = \|x - c\| \tag{21}$$

where c is the centre of the RBF. The kernel of radial basis functions is considered cubic and is expressed as:

$$\varphi(s) = s^3 \tag{22}$$

where $\varphi(s)$ is the kernel which belongs to the category of polyharmonic splines. An RBF interpolator fits scalar-valued observations $d = [d_1, \dots, d_n]^T$ which are from locations $y = [y_1, \dots, y_n]$. The RBF interpolator can be written in the form [60]:

$$f(x) = K(x, y)a + P(x)b \tag{23}$$

where $K(x, y)$ is a matrix of RBF $\varphi(s)$ with centres c at y evaluated at the points x , and $P(x)$ is a matrix of monomials, which span polynomials with the specified degree (equal to 1 in our case), evaluated at x . In this study, the RBF interpolator is fitted to the X_{train} and y_{train} which can be formulated as:

$$I_{RBF} = f(X_{train}, y_{train}) \tag{24}$$

where X_{train} is four-dimensional input matrix of independent variables and y_{train} represents the output vector of the dependent variable in training set based on the experimental data. The coefficients a and b in Eq. (23) are the solution to the linear equations that can be formulated as:

$$(K(y, y) + \lambda I)a + P(y)b = d \tag{25}$$

where λ is a non-negative smoothing (regularization) parameter that regulates how well we want to fit the data and I is the identity matrix. The data are fitted exactly when the smoothing parameter $\lambda = 0$ [61]. However, if the $\lambda = 0$ each data point location must be distinct. In this study, the smoothing parameter $\lambda \in \{1.0 \times 10^{-4}, 2.5 \times 10^{-4}, \dots, 2.5, 7.5\}$ with the total amount of 20 values.

Finally, the augmented logarithmic fatigue life y_{aug} for each value of the smoothing parameter λ is calculated using a fitted interpolator I_{RBF} . The applied formula can be written as follows:

$$y_{aug} = I_{RBF}(X_{aug}) \tag{26}$$

where X_{aug} is the augmented input matrix of independent variables. In addition, final values of y_{aug} for each investigated value of λ are

Fig. 6. Calculated values of y_{aug} for each value of smoothing parameter λ of RBF interpolation.

shown in Fig. 6 using a boxplot.

4.3. Hyperparameters optimization of the GBR model

4.3.1. Tree-structured Parzen estimator

The variant Bayesian optimization (BO) algorithm called Tree-structured Parzen estimator (TPE) [62] is applied in this study. The TPE algorithm is coded in the Python’s library named Optuna 3.1.0 using function called TPESampler [63]. The TPE converts the hyperparameter space (configuration) into a non-parametric density distribution. The standard optimization problem of hyperparameter optimization (HPO) can be defined as:

$$\omega^* = \operatorname{argmin}_{\omega \in \Omega} f(\omega) \tag{27}$$

$$f = \sum_{i=1}^k \overline{RMSE}_i \tag{28}$$

where ω^* denotes the optimal hyperparameter configuration, Ω represents the search space, $f(\omega)$ signifies an objective function and i is the number of the i -th trial of TPE. In this paper the average root mean square error \overline{RMSE}_i is used as an objective function to be minimized after k trials of HPO and can be expressed as:

$$\overline{RMSE}_i = \frac{1}{l} \sum_{j=1}^l RMSE_{i,j} \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, k; j = 1, 2, \dots, l \tag{29}$$

where l is the number of cross-validations (described in more detail in the following subchapter), the formula of $RMSE$ is expressed by Eq. (33). The values of optimization hyperparameters ω in the space Ω are sampled in logarithmic or linear domain from defined intervals. At the starting point of the TPE, the initial distribution is engaged by sampling the response entity $\{\omega^{(i)}, y^{(i)}, i \in [1, k]\}$ where y is the corresponding validation or fitness value. Then, the TPE defines two densities of hyperparameter space Ω using $p(\omega|y)$:

$$p(\omega|y) = \begin{cases} l(\omega) & \text{if } y < y^* \\ g(\omega) & \text{if } y \geq y^* \end{cases} \tag{30}$$

where $l(\omega)$ is the density formed using the observation $\{\omega^{(i)}\}$ so that the corresponding loss $f(\omega^{(i)})$ was less than y^* , and $g(\omega)$ is the density formed using the remaining observations. The TPE algorithm depends on y^* which is larger than the best observed $f(\omega)$ when $l(\omega)$ is formed. The TPE algorithm chooses y^* to be some quantile δ (usually set to 15% [64]) of the calculated y values, so that $p(y <$

Fig. 7. Diagram of the HPO technique using the TPE and 20-fold CV, $k = 200$.

$y^*) = \delta$, but specific model for $p(y)$ is not needed. In this manner, the choice of the optimal hyperparameters ω^* is based on a set of the best observations and their distribution. Further, an expected improvement (EI) is expressed as follows:

$$EI(\omega) = \frac{l(\omega)}{g(\omega)} \tag{31}$$

The optimal hyperparameter configuration ω^* that maximizes the EI is chosen at each trial. By maintaining a sorted list of observed variables in the observation history H, the runtime of each trial of the TPE algorithm can scale linearly in |H| and linearly in the number of dimensions being optimized.

4.3.2. Hyperparameters of the GBR model

The overall process of HPO is shown in Fig. 7. Prior to the optimization process, the hyperparameters of the GBR model must be set. For the TPE algorithm, the search space Ω for hyperparameters is defined as:

$$\Omega = \{DT_M, DT_D, DT_S, \eta\} \tag{32}$$

where DT_M represents the number of decision trees used in the GBR model, DT_D denotes the maximum depth of the decision trees, DT_S is the minimal portion of samples to be split in the nodes, and η represents the learning rate. The defined values of the hyperparameters are shown in Table 3.

For the HPO, only the training sets without augmentation ($D_{train,exp}$) or with augmentation ($D_{train,aug}$) are used (see Fig. 7). $D_{train,exp}$ and $D_{train,aug}$ represent experimental observations and the augmented dataset, respectively. Values of $D_{train,aug}$ are dependent on the value of the smoothing parameter λ used during the RBF interpolation. The 20-fold cross-validation (CV) technique is used. This technique splits the whole training set into 19 training subsets and one validation subset in each round of CV (see Fig. 7). The splitting is performed to prevent biasing the HPO algorithm. When $D_{train,exp}$ is used for the training, the 20-fold CV can also be expressed as leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV) because the total amount of samples in $D_{train,exp}$ is 20. The LOOCV procedure creates maximum splits. In other words, the number of splits is equal to the number of samples in the overall training set. The LOOCV approach is generally applied if the dataset size is considered small [65]. This detailed CV technique should provide the most accurate HPO for the GBR model without using the augmented dataset. Hence, it will be applied as a comparison criterion for the prediction ability of the GBR model that employs the augmented dataset.

After each round of the 20-fold CV, the model accuracy is evaluated. This study applies the RMSE as a criterion for the prediction ability of the model. The RMSE is observed during the CV for each round. When all rounds are finished, the average root mean squared error \overline{RMSE} is calculated. Furthermore, when all trials ($k = 200$) of TPE are finished, the lowest \overline{RMSE} is evaluated. The state with the lowest \overline{RMSE} observed is assumed to be the GBR model with optimized hyperparameters.

4.4. Criterion of model accuracy

The root mean squared error RMSE and coefficient of determination R^2 were selected and evaluated as a criterion of the GBR model prediction accuracy. The closer the value of RMSE is to zero or R^2 is to one, the more accurate the fatigue life prediction of the GBR model is. The formulas of RMSE and R^2 are expressed in Eqs. (33) and (34), respectively:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_{true,i} - y_{pred,i})^2}{n}} \tag{33}$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_{true,i} - y_{pred,i})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_{true,i} - \bar{y}_{true})^2} \tag{34}$$

$$\bar{y}_{true} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_{true,i} \tag{35}$$

where n is the number of values, $y_{true,i}$ is the validation value of logarithmic fatigue life, $y_{pred,i}$ is the value of logarithmic fatigue life predicted by the GBR model and \bar{y}_{true} is the arithmetic mean of validation values of logarithmic fatigue life.

Table 3
Properties and interval of tuned hyperparameters of the GBR model.

Hyperparameter	Data type	Domain	Interval
DT_M	Integer	Logarithmic	[1, 500]
DT_D	Integer	Linear	[1, 40]
DT_S	Float	Linear	[0.050, 1.0]
η	Float	Logarithmic	[0.001, 1.0]

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Optimized hyperparameters

The HPO of GBR was performed for two types of configurations. The GBR model is trained on the training set without augmentation ($D_{train,exp}$) or with augmentation ($D_{train,aug}$), see Fig. 7. The optimized GBR model by TPE algorithm for considered configuration with the optimized hyperparameters ω^* and the corresponding prediction model accuracy measured by \overline{RMSE} are recorded in Table 4. To illustrate, the optimization process with configuration using the augmented training set $D_{train,aug}$ and the smoothing parameter $\lambda = 0.75$ is shown in Fig. 8.

5.2. Fatigue life prediction

Finally, the prediction of fatigue life y_{pred} is estimated by retraining the GBR model with the optimized hyperparameters (see Fig. 4). The y_{pred} can be expressed as:

$$y_{pred} = \text{GBR}(X_{test}) \tag{36}$$

where $\text{GBR}(\bullet)$ represents the GBR model with the optimized hyperparameters and X_{test} the experimental test set, respectively. The computed values of y_{pred} are then compared with y_{test} and the model test accuracy by R^2 and $RMSE$ is evaluated. The calculated values are listed in Table 5 and shown in Fig. 9. In Fig. 9A and Fig. 9B is shown the prediction accuracy for test set (unseen data) without augmented dataset using red dash-and-dot line as a threshold. The test prediction accuracy with the augmented dataset is higher for several values of λ . The highest prediction accuracy was achieved for $\lambda = 0.75$ with the values of $R_{test}^2 = 0.953$ and $RMSE_{test} = 0.105$, respectively. The improvement of the prediction ability of the GBR model with an augmented dataset is delivered compared to the configuration without augmentation ($R_{test}^2 = 0.860$, $RMSE_{test} = 0.181$), resulting in increasing the most the R_{test}^2 by 10.81% and decreasing the $RMSE_{test}$ by 41.99%.

To demonstrate the effectiveness of prediction accuracy for each sample from the test set, the absolute percentage error (APE) is used. The APE is defined by the following formula:

$$APE = \frac{|y_{test,i} - y_{pred,i}|}{y_{test,i}} \times 100 \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, n_{test} \tag{37}$$

In Fig. 10 is shown comparison (for $n_{test} = 9$) between experimental (y_{test}) and predicted logarithmic fatigue life (y_{pred}) without augmentation (only hypertuned GBR model was used) or with augmentation (RBF interpolation with $\lambda = 0.75$ and hypertuned GBR model were used) using goodness-of-fit plot (see Fig. 10A) and error plot per test sample using APE (see Fig. 10B). The maximal APE is calculated for 9-th sample (from overall dataset) for modeling without augmented set and with augmented set. Nevertheless, the values

Table 4

The results of HPO of the GBR model without augmentation ($D_{train,exp}$) and with augmentation ($D_{train,aug}$) using various values (20 in total) of the smoothing parameter λ of RBF interpolation.

#Model	Training set	n_{train}	n_{aug}	λ	\overline{RMSE}	#Trial	Hyperparameter			
							DT_M	DT_D	DT_S	η
1	$D_{train,exp}$	20	-*	-*	0.1305	141	137	36	0.702	0.068
2	$D_{train,aug}$	20	1000	0.00010	0.0141	54	135	30	0.504	0.380
3				0.00025	0.0140	131	210	17	0.487	0.143
4				0.00050	0.0142	68	29	3	0.116	0.609
5				0.00075	0.0117	194	126	3	0.066	0.312
6				0.0010	0.0111	171	187	3	0.134	0.217
7				0.0025	0.0098	196	128	3	0.112	0.151
8				0.0050	0.0081	67	352	2	0.172	0.570
9				0.0075	0.0090	175	128	2	0.130	0.313
10				0.010	0.0089	90	338	32	0.107	0.105
11				0.025	0.0084	64	226	13	0.144	0.085
12				0.050	0.0071	161	295	22	0.229	0.142
13				0.075	0.0067	194	401	16	0.201	0.075
14				0.10	0.0059	199	296	20	0.222	0.230
15				0.25	0.0050	193	499	33	0.216	0.023
16				0.50	0.0047	110	500	12	0.232	0.132
17				0.75	0.0046	113	193	26	0.551	0.500
18				1.00	0.0047	91	246	15	0.470	0.096
19				2.50	0.0048	197	292	17	0.579	0.296
20				5.00	0.0040	119	176	28	0.574	0.502
21				7.50	0.0043	197	87	16	0.630	0.489

* Augmented set is not used.

Fig. 8. HPO process for each trial of TPE using the augmented training set $D_{train, aug}$ and the smoothing parameter $\lambda = 0.75$.

Table 5

Evaluation of the prediction accuracy of retrained optimized GBR model without augmentation ($D_{train, exp}$) and with augmentation ($D_{train, aug}$) using various values (20 in total) of the smoothing parameter λ of RBF interpolation.

#Model	Test set	n_{test}	Training set	n_{train}	n_{aug}	λ	R^2_{test}	R^2_{train}	$RMSE_{test}$	$RMSE_{train}$
1	D_{test}	9	$D_{train, exp}$	20	-*	-*	0.860	0.910	0.181	0.152
2	D_{test}	9	$D_{train, aug}$	20	1000	0.00010	0.880	0.989	0.168	0.063
3						0.00025	0.882	0.989	0.166	0.062
4						0.00050	0.775	0.988	0.230	0.063
5						0.00075	0.768	0.992	0.233	0.052
6						0.0010	0.833	0.993	0.198	0.050
7						0.0025	0.795	0.994	0.219	0.044
8						0.0050	0.807	0.995	0.213	0.036
9						0.0075	0.836	0.994	0.196	0.039
10						0.010	0.781	0.994	0.226	0.040
11						0.025	0.765	0.995	0.235	0.038
12						0.050	0.866	0.996	0.177	0.031
13						0.075	0.799	0.996	0.217	0.030
14						0.10	0.909	0.997	0.146	0.026
15						0.25	0.843	0.998	0.192	0.022
16						0.50	0.942	0.998	0.117	0.021
17						0.75	0.953	0.998	0.105	0.020
18						1.0	0.946	0.998	0.112	0.021
19						2.5	0.940	0.998	0.119	0.021
20						5.0	0.917	0.999	0.140	0.018
21						7.5	0.939	0.998	0.120	0.019

* Augmented set is not used.

of APE are different for each solution. Explicitly, the APE of prediction accuracy without and with augmented set is 7.88% and 4.36%, respectively.

The prediction accuracy ($R^2_{test} = 0.953$) with augmented set ($\lambda = 0.75$) is higher in comparison with paper of Salvati et al. [31] where authors used defect-based physic-informed ANN model. The achieved prediction accuracy in the study $R^2_{test} = 0.591$ is lower by 37.99%. The dataset used for ML model contents only 12 samples. The proposed algorithm for dataset augmentation in our paper could improve the prediction accuracy performance. Another study of Shi et al. [32] proposed the GMM for dataset augmentation. The ANN, SVR and RF models predicted fatigue life. The original defect-based dataset contents 45 samples. The highest prediction performance on dimensionality reduced datasets (using Smith-Watson-Topper correction) is 0.884, 0.836 and 0.962 evaluated by ANN, SVR and RF models, respectively. It can be concluded, the prediction accuracy using ANN and SVR is slightly lower in comparison with the present work. However, the prediction performance is almost equivalent using the RF model.

6. Conclusions

In the presented paper, the fatigue life prediction of AM Ti-6Al-4V samples was evaluated using the ML supervised GBR model. The original dataset was based on the observed data from μ -CT measurement and fatigue tests. The μ -CT measurement was performed prior

Fig. 9. Results of model prediction accuracy using retrained optimized GBR model for each value of the smoothing parameter λ evaluated for (A) training and test accuracy measured by R^2 ; (B) training and test accuracy measured by RMSE.

Fig. 10. Comparison of results between experimental (y_{test}) and predicted logarithmic fatigue life (y_{pred}) using retrained optimized GBR model without and with augmented training set ($\lambda = 0.75$) shown by (A) goodness-of-fit plot; (B) APE per sample.

to the fatigue test and quantified the internal defects induced by the AM technique in terms of size, location and sphericity. Since the original dataset size was considered small, the study proposed a novel approach for the dataset augmentation. The research conclusions are summarized as follows:

- (1) The inverse transform sampling method was used for augmentation of independent variables and multivariate RBF interpolation with various values (20 in total) of the smoothing parameter λ was applied as augmentation technique for fatigue life.
- (2) For comparison analysis, two types of training sets were used to train the GBR model. The simulation was at first performed using the training set without augmentation ($D_{train,exp}$) and then using the augmented training set ($D_{train,aug}$). Totally 21 GBR models were created.

- (3) For the HPO of the GBR model, the 20-fold CV and the TPE algorithm with 200 trials were employed. Furthermore, all GBR models with optimized hyperparameters were retrained and used for the prediction of fatigue life for a test set.
- (4) The model test accuracy was evaluated and compared for both approaches of trained GBR model. For the simulation with an augmented dataset with RBF smoothing parameter $\lambda = 0.75$, the test accuracy increased by 10.81% up to 0.953 in terms of the R^2 , respectively decreased by 41.99% down to 0.105 in terms of $RMSE$.
- (5) Therefore, it can be concluded that the proposed dataset augmentation technique was efficient. The proposed algorithm using a ML method showed high precision for predicting the fatigue life of AM Ti-6Al-4V parts.
- (6) To achieve an even higher prediction accuracy, in further studies another type of kernel for the RBF interpolation, different interpolation technique or ML model should be considered. In addition to that, more independent variables should be used, such as the residual stress, used material, types of AM, stress amplitude levels, a broader lifetime range for fatigue, and different stress ratios.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jan Horňas: Visualization, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization, Writing – original draft. **Jiří Běhal:** Validation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Petr Homola:** Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Radek Doubrava:** Validation, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Martin Holzleitner:** Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Sascha Senck:** Validation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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